

Supplementary Table 4. Main demographic characteristics of the validation cohort of AD and HC from ADNI-3

	AD (n=22)	HC (n=19)
Age (years)	73.65±9.87	76.48±4.09
Women n (%)	7 (32%)	11 (58%)
Years of education	15.73±2.60	16.95±1.99
MMSE	21.91±3.45	29.26±1.15